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CONTENTS

FINANCING OF SMALL BUSINESSES THROUGH INVESTMENT LOANS BY COMMERCIAL BANKS.....	15
Yangiboyev F.B.	
INTEGRATION OF THE TRANSPORT SECTOR INTO THE GREEN ECONOMY AND IMPACT ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: ECOLOGICAL TRANSFORMATION AND INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS	20
Narziyev Umidjon Bakhriylayevich	
FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN INCREASING THE INVESTMENT ACTIVITY OF JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES	24
Begamov. S.X.	
AN ENHANCED FINANCING MODEL FOR STARTUP PROJECTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS OF UZBEKISTAN	27
Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna	
STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING INVESTMENT POTENTIAL.....	32
Tillayeva Barno Ramizitdinovna	
THE IMPORTANCE OF USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HOTEL MANAGEMENT.....	36
Husenova Madina Farkhodovna	
MARKETPLACES AND ECONOMIC SECURITY IN UZBEKISTAN: RISKS AND REGULATION	42
Umarkhodjayeva Zaynabkhon Nodirkhonovna	
TECHNOLOGICAL STRENGTH AND PROPERTIES OF METAL OF AUSTENITIC JOINTS DURING WELDING WITH VARIOUS FLUXES.....	47
Khudoykulov Nurilla Zikirillaevich, Khudoyorov Sardor Sadullaevich	
MODERN SYSTEMS OF PRODUCT COST CALCULATION: METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS AND DIRECTIONS OF PRACTICAL TRANSFORMATION	51
Abdumalik Abdiraximovich Tulyaganov	
SUPPORTING ECONOMIC EXPANSION AND MAXIMIZING PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY WITHIN A MARKET ECONOMY.....	56
Aytmuratov Qutlimurat Jalgasovich	
SUCCESS FACTORS OF DIFFERENTIATION STRATEGY IN A MARKET ECONOMY.....	62
Sodiqov Miraxror Abbos ugli	
THE “MISSING MIDDLE” PROBLEM IN SOCIAL PROTECTION SYSTEMS AND MECHANISMS FOR ADDRESSING IT	67
Farrukh Juraqulovich Bafoev	
IMPROVING POPULATION INVESTMENT ACTIVITY THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF BANK BROKERAGE SERVICES AND FINANCIAL LITERACY IN FORMING A SECURITIES PORTFOLIO IN THE KHOREZM REGION	72
Bakhtiyorov Khudaybergan Hamdam ugli	
DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE SECTOR AND ITS IMPACT ON POVERTY REDUCTION.....	79
Dauletmuratov Adilbay Mirzabaevich	
THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF A SYNERGETIC APPROACH IN DEVELOPING THE MANAGEMENT SKILLS OF SCHOOL DIRECTORS.....	84
Yusupova Dilnoza Fayzullayevna	
REGIONAL INNOVATION DEVELOPMENT INDICATORS AND THEIR EVALUATION SYSTEM	89
Xamrayev Quvvat Iskandarovich	
GADGETS AND VALUES: HOW DOES THE VIRTUAL WORLD IMPACT THE EDUCATION OF YOUTH?	97
Makhmudova Sohiba Ravshan kizi, Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli	
WAYS TO IMPROVE SERVICE QUALITY AND SAFETY IN THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES	101
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
DIRECTIONS FOR INCREASING HOUSEHOLD INCOMES BASED ON FOREIGN EXPERIENCE.....	104
Eshbaeva Shahnoza Faxriddinovna	

IMPROVING METHODS FOR DETECTING FRAUD CASES IN CURRENT ASSET AUDITS.....	108
Mavlyanova Dilobar Makhkamovna	
GLOBAL TRENDS IN WORLD MARKETS AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNATIONAL TRADE	113
Meliqulov Abduhalil Norinovich	
THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF FORMING AND APPLYING THE INTEGRATION MECHANISM OF SMALL BUSINESS	119
Rustambek Ibragimovich Israilov	
THE IMPORTANCE OF USING PERFORMANCE INDICATORS IN IMPROVING ROAD MANAGEMENT METHODS.....	125
Sirojiddin Yadgarov	
WAYS TO IMPROVE BANKING EFFICIENCY IN THE CONDITIONS OF TRANSFORMATION.....	131
Babakhanova Dildora Rustamovna	
THE ROLE OF PROGRAM-BASED BUDGETING MECHANISMS IN ENSURING STATE FINANCIAL SECURITY	137
Abduganiyev Uchkun Khabibulla ugli	
ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF PUBLIC FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY ON SOCIAL JUSTICE THROUGH PEFA AND CEQ METHODOLOGIES.....	143
Zokirjonov Muhammadsodiq Ravshanbek ugli	
MANAGERIAL MECHANISMS OF CORPORATE HYBRID BUSINESS MODELS: FINTECH INTEGRATION IN E-PAYMENT SYSTEMS OF UZBEKISTAN	151
Mokhirakhon Abdullaeva	
TOKENIZATION OF REAL SECTOR ASSETS AND DEEPENING OF CAPITAL MARKETS: A NEW FINANCIAL ARCHITECTURE FOR EMERGING ECONOMIES	156
Oybek Qo'shboqov	
TECHNOLOGIES OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN OPTICAL COMMUNICATION AND THEIR INTEGRATION INTO INTELLIGENT TUTORING SYSTEMS.....	162
Maxamadov Rustam Xabibullayevich, Djamatov Mustafa Xatamovich	
APPROACHES TO ENHANCING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF GOVERNMENT SUPPORT FOR SMALL BUSINESSES IN THE REGION	169
Madraimova Marxamat Raximberganovna	
INNOVATIVE WAYS TO INCREASE THE INVESTMENT CAPACITY OF REGIONS BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES.....	174
Qabilov Anvar Eshpulatovich	
TAXATION OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES AND THE ORGANIZATION OF THEIR ACCOUNTING SYSTEMS.....	179
Abdullayev Abdurauf	
DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF THE VEGETABLE FARMING SECTOR IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	183
Sobir Xasanov	
AI FOR TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TO UNIVERSITY STUDENTS.....	191
Nurzhanova Zhainash, Rajapova Guldon	
REVIEW OF THERMAL STRENGTHENING METHODS FOR ROLLING ROLLS MADE OF ALLOY STEELS USED IN THE PRODUCTION OF SEAMLESS PIPES	198
Saydumarov Botir Muradovich, Xasanov Kamoliddin Akmal o'g'li, Ergashev Davron Ortiq o'g'li, Saydumarov Botir Muradovich	
IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT IN ENHANCING THE COUNTRY'S INTERNATIONAL IMAGE: IN THE EXAMPLE OF SOUTH KOREA.....	203
Kurolov Maksud Obitovich	
SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF TASHKENT CITY: TRENDS AND KEY INDICATORS.....	212
Karimova Shirin Zokhid qizi	
PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS INFLUENCING PROCRASTINATION AMONG GENERATION Z UNIVERSITY STUDENTS.....	216
Abdukaxxorova Durdona, Qadamova Rayhona, Muhammadova Shaxzoda, Salimov Ozodbek, Hojiyeva Iroda Avezovna	

IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF PRIVATE SCHOOLS BASED ON INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES.....	222
Shohida Esanova	
ASSESSMENT OF TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY IN CENTRAL ASIAN TELECOMMUNICATION OPERATORS USING THE DEA-CCR MODEL: THE EXPERIENCE OF UZBEKTELEKOM AK	230
Salimova Husniya Rustamovna	
DETERMINANTS OF MUTUAL TRADE BETWEEN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE CIS COUNTRIES	235
Munisa Turdibaeva	
INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEM IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS.....	241
Mekhmonaliev Ulugbek Erkinjon ugli	
PROSPECTS FOR ENSURING SUSTAINABLE GROWTH IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES THROUGH THE USE OF GREEN TECHNOLOGIES	248
Abbosbek Jurayev	
COMPLIANCE OF BANKING AI SYSTEMS WITH EU AI ACT REQUIREMENTS AND THEIR ROLE IN RISK MANAGEMENT	253
Usmonov Faridun F., Zainalov Zh.R.	
A MODEL FOR DETECTING URBAN INFRASTRUCTURE PROBLEMS IN CITIZENS' APPEALS BASED ON GEOLOCATION FEATURES	258
Mallayev Oybek Usmankulovich, Gazatov Jamoliddin Abduvoidovich, Aliyev Jaloliddin Kokand oglu	
DETERMINATION OF THE INFORMATIVENESS OF INPUT PRINTS USING THE MULTI-CRITERIA DISPERSION METHOD	264
Turapov Ulugbek Urazkulovich, Akulbayev Musabek Islamovich, Dzhantayeva Sholpan Kalmakhanovna, Madalievna Gul'nar Urazalievna	
ANALYSIS OF MACROECONOMIC INDICATORS OF RECREATIONAL TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	269
Polatova Mavluda Sanjar qizi	
OPTIMIZATION OF MANAGEMENT PROCESSES OF TOURISM INDUSTRIES THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES.....	273
Saidova Dilfuza Abdufattohovna	
MODERNIZING AUDIT PLANNING STRATEGIES IN EMERGING ECONOMIES: CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS FOR ISA IMPLEMENTATION IN UZBEKISTAN	280
Saidova Sevarakhon Abdumumin kizi	
INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN ACCOUNTING FOR LONG-TERM ASSETS AND ITS APPLICATION	285
Gozieva Mokhira Rustamovna	
SCIENTIFIC BASIS FOR THE CLASSIFICATION OF TERRITORIES AND THE APPLICATION OF CORRECTION COEFFICIENTS.....	290
Dovutov Fakhridin Javliyevich	
MANAGEMENT OF THE PROCESSING TECHNOLOGY FOR COCOONS MODIFIED USING A NEW COMPOSITION BASED ON STANDARD REQUIREMENTS	296
Makhmudov Umidjon Bahodir ugli, Turdialiyev Umid Mukhtaraliyevich, Sulaymonov Sharifjon Abdumanabovich	
STUDY ON THE EFFECT OF THERMOPLASTIC DEFORMATION ON THE MICROSTRUCTURE OF XH56MBK10 ALLOY	302
Berdiyev Darob Muratovich, Saydumarov Botir Muradovich, Tashmatov Ravshan Kobilovich, Baxtiyorov Rustam Ravshan o'g'li	
THE IMPORTANCE OF PROMOTING COMPANIES' PARTICIPATION IN THE STOCK MARKET.....	306
Mamatalliev Babur Saidnazar ugli	
EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF FINANCIAL LEVERS IN ATTRACTING FOREIGN INVESTMENTS IN JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES.....	312
Ibragimov Ganijon Gayratovich	
HR STRATEGIES FOR HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT IN ORGANIZATIONS	316
Zaynutdinova Umida, Kholisakhon Nuriddinova	

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS IN THE INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATION OF ACCOUNTING AND
AUDITING SYSTEMS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY..... 324
Jumanazarov Ruzimurod, Rabbimov Elbek

CONTENTS

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS IN THE INSTITUTIONAL TRANSFORMATION OF ACCOUNTING AND AUDITING SYSTEMS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract: This article examines the institutional transformation of accounting and auditing systems in the digital economy. It highlights the role of Artificial Intelligence, Big Data, and cloud technologies, and provides a comparative analysis of global and local software solutions. The study identifies key challenges such as regulatory gaps, skills shortages, and cybersecurity risks. Scientific and practical recommendations are proposed to improve the system.

Key words: accounting, auditing, artificial intelligence, digital transformation, cybersecurity, IFRS.

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary global economic landscape, the digital economy has become an integral foundation of the financial system. The rapid evolution of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data analytics, and cloud computing is fundamentally altering how enterprises operate. These processes have a direct and profound impact on accounting and auditing systems, necessitating their urgent institutional transformation. Institutional transformation implies not merely the adoption of new software, but a comprehensive redesign of regulatory frameworks, educational standards, and operational mentalities.

Global market statistics clearly illustrate the scale of this technological shift. According to Fortune Business Insights, the global accounting software market was valued at \$20.9 billion in 2025 and is projected to reach \$42.17 billion by 2032, exhibiting a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 10.5%. This exponential growth confirms the aggressive transition from traditional bookkeeping to intelligent, cloud-based ecosystems. Similarly, the Republic of Uzbekistan has gained substantial practical and theoretical experience in this domain. Significant efforts have been made to adapt 1C software to national legislation and to develop domestic solutions such as 1UZ, BEM, and UzASBO to digitalize accounting processes across both private and public sectors.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The digital transformation of accounting and auditing has been widely explored by international and domestic scholars. Adeyelu (2024) and Barri (2025) highlight the profound impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and automation in minimizing human errors and shifting traditional financial workflows. Furthermore, Musgrove (2025) and Davidson (2024) evaluate the practical benefits of leading global accounting software platforms.

Regarding local implementation, Qudbiyev (2021) and Kunduzova (2020) emphasize the critical need to transition to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) to attract foreign investments. The practical integration of IT into Uzbekistan's accounting landscape and the CIS region is specifically analyzed by Teshaboyev (2023), Oralbaeva (2023), and Shamina & Filimonov (2018). The macroeconomic importance of ICT in Central Asia is confirmed by Shodiev et al. (2021). However, digitalization introduces severe institutional risks, such as data breaches, which are highlighted as a major financial threat in the IBM Security Report (2024).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology is based on a systematic approach, utilizing logical and comparative analysis, induction, and deduction. A comparative functional analysis was conducted between internationally recognized accounting software (Xero, QuickBooks) and domestic platforms (UzASBO, 1UZ). Furthermore, statistical data from authoritative global research centers (IBM, Gartner, ACCA) and academic literature were synthesized to critically evaluate the institutional challenges hindering the digital transformation of the accounting and auditing sectors (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of Global and Local Accounting Software Systems

Criteria	Xero / QuickBooks (Global)	UzASBO / 1UZ / BEM (Local)
Accessibility	Cloud-based with global access	Primarily local or hybrid cloud solutions
Compliance	IFRS and international standards	National tax legislation (Uzbekistan)
Functionality	Advanced analytics and AI-driven features	Basic automation and tax reporting
Integration	Bank synchronization and third-party integrations	Limited integration capabilities
Cost	Subscription-based (relatively high)	Affordable, often state-supported
Target Users	SMEs and international companies	Local businesses and government-related entities
AI Capabilities	Predictive analytics and automation	Limited implementation of AI
Real-time Reporting	Fully available	Partially available

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The automation of accounting systems dramatically enhances the speed and accuracy of financial reporting, facilitating a smoother transition to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). In the global market, cloud-based platforms such as "Xero," "QuickBooks Online," "FreshBooks," and "Sage Intacct" have established dominance. These platforms go beyond basic automated reporting by offering real-time bank synchronization and predictive cash-flow analysis. In Uzbekistan, "UzASBO" has shown high efficiency for budget organizations, while "1UZ" and "BEM" are heavily utilized in the private sector due to their strict compliance with the national tax code.

The integration of AI is transforming the role of the accountant. According to Gartner, AI-driven automation allows finance and accounting professionals to save an average of 5.4 hours per week by eliminating routine manual data entry. Furthermore, the "Big Four" auditing firms (Deloitte, PwC, EY, and KPMG) are investing billions into AI auditing platforms (e.g., EY Helix, KPMG Clara) to conduct real-time anomaly detection across 100% of transaction datasets, rather than relying on traditional random sampling.

Despite the clear advantages of digital technologies, the institutional transformation of accounting and auditing faces several critical hurdles:

1. Shortage of Qualified Personnel (The Skills Gap): The digital economy demands that modern accountants possess hybrid skills encompassing finance, IT, data analytics, and AI management. According to the Association of Chartered Certified Accountants (ACCA), while over 80% of finance leaders acknowledge the necessity of AI, less than 40% of organizations actively invest in upskilling their accounting staff. This creates a severe technological skills gap in the labor market.

2. **Cybersecurity and Data Privacy Threats:** Digital systems store massive volumes of highly sensitive financial data, making them prime targets for cyberattacks. According to IBM's Cost of a Data Breach Report, the average cost of a data breach in the financial sector has reached \$6.08 million, which is significantly higher than the global average.

3. **Undeveloped Technological Infrastructure for SMEs:** Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) often lack the financial capital to invest in advanced Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems, licensed AI audit tools, and necessary cybersecurity protocols, leaving them marginalized in the digital transformation process (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Key Challenges and Risks in the Digital Transformation of Accounting and Auditing

To systematically resolve these problems, a multi-faceted approach is required:

- **Modernization of Legislation:** Governments must adopt specialized normative acts on “Digital Accounting and Auditing” based on international standards. This includes legalizing digital evidence for audits, regulating crypto-asset accounting, and establishing clear guidelines for the use of AI in financial decision-making.
- **Educational Reform:** Higher education institutions must integrate courses such as “ERP Systems,” “AI in Accounting,” and “Financial Data Analytics” into the core curriculum of Accounting and Audit degree programs.
- **Enhancing Cybersecurity Standards:** It should be mandatory for financial data processors to comply with international security protocols (e.g., ISO/IEC 27001). The implementation of Blockchain technology can also be introduced to ensure the immutability and transparency of audit trails.
- **State Support for SMEs:** Providing tax incentives or technology grants to small businesses that implement licensed cloud accounting systems will bridge the digital divide.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTION

The automation of accounting systems and the integration of artificial intelligence serve as catalysts for unprecedented efficiency in financial management.

As demonstrated by the research, modern technological solutions accelerate transaction processing, perform deep predictive analytics, and minimize human error. However, true progress in this field requires more than just the adoption of software; it necessitates a profound institutional transformation.

Firstly, the role of the accountant is shifting from a traditional “number cruncher” to a strategic financial advisor. To support this evolution, educational systems must urgently pivot towards STEM-integrated financial training.

Secondly, regulatory bodies face the critical task of rewriting the rules of the financial ecosystem. Without a robust legal framework that recognizes smart contracts, digital assets, and AI-generated audit reports, technological advancement will outpace legal compliance, leading to market instability.

Thirdly, as cyber threats grow in sophistication and financial impact, embedding advanced cybersecurity measures into accounting infrastructure is no longer optional but a fundamental requirement for business survival.

Ultimately, addressing these institutional bottlenecks through collaborative efforts between the state, educational institutions, and the private sector will ensure a secure, transparent, and globally competitive accounting and auditing system in the era of the digital economy.

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